

Profitability landscapes for competitive photovoltaic self-consumption

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Abstract

Photovoltaic self-consumption (PVSC) is a central element of the energy transition. However, retail electricity tariffs have not adapted to the emerging phenomenon of demand-side generation. We introduce the concept of profitability landscapes to evaluate the effects of a cost-reflective retail tariff and a competitive PVSC regulation on prosumers' returns depending on system costs and self-consumption share. The trade-off between these two elements reveals the value of demand flexibility. We find that PVSC would be profitable in most European countries when external costs are internalized, confirm the diminishing marginal returns on demand flexibility and quantify the effects of prices, insolation and profitability on the value of demand flexibility.

Keywords

Photovoltaic self-consumption, decarbonization, competitiveness, retail electricity market, energy transition.

Highlights

- We evaluate the effect of a cost-reflective retail tariff on PVSC profitability.
- We introduce the concept of profitability landscape for PVSC.
- We quantify the value of demand flexibility for prosumers.
- Competitive PVSC is profitable in most European countries.
- Diminishing marginal returns on demand flexibility.

1. Introduction

Photovoltaic self-consumption (PVSC) is at the center of the energy transition. The “5Ds” (decarbonization, digitalization, decentralization, democratization, deregulation) that characterize the main trends in the transformation of the electricity system involve disruptions caused by the possibility of producing energy directly at the demand side (Moghaddam et al., 2022). PVSC contributes to *decarbonization* as a zero carbon electricity generation technology (Victoria et al., 2021). *Digitalization* will allow demand flexibility, increasing thus PVSC profitability and boosting its diffusion (IEA, 2017). PVSC is the cornerstone of energy *decentralization* and *democratization*, as it allows households and firms become producers (Lee et al., 2018). Finally, because PVSC is a new phenomenon, new regulations will have to be developed to allow the participation of all interested agents in this new market.

Whereas small-scale PV is generally more expensive in unit terms than large-scale installations (IRENA, 2022), the investment needs to achieve the Paris goal require a wide range of solutions, beyond the lowest cost options, to speed up the adoption of zero-carbon technologies (IEA, 2021). PVSC has the potential to multiply the amount of investment directed toward the energy transition as it allows a wide range of new actors (individuals, communities and companies) to become energy producers. PVSC presents additional co-benefits, such as higher demand flexibility (Gržanić et al., 2022), which reduces peak demand and thus system cost, and the lower landscape impacts of building-integrated PV than large-scale installations.

The main policy goal so far has been to promote the adoption of PV, both centralized and distributed, to achieve technological maturity (Dijkgraaf et al., 2018). This has created certain imbalances due to the rapid evolution of the PV sector, such as profitability and diffusion bubbles in the case of Feed-in Tariffs (López Prol, 2018), fixed cost recovery problems (Borenstein, 2016) and equity concerns (Simshauser, 2016). As PV becomes a mature technology, such aggressive incentive policies are no longer necessary (Borenstein, 2022), and regulations tend to transition to a competitive setting in which external costs are progressively internalized (e.g., by the implementation of carbon prices), and technologies compete in equal conditions in wholesale and, for the case of PVSC, also retail markets.

For these reasons, we first study how a cost-reflective retail electricity tariff and a competitive regulation for PVSC would look like (Section 2). Then we assess whether PVSC systems would be economically viable in these conditions in Europe (Section 3). Because prosumers can maximize profitability by increasing the share of self-consumption from their PV system, we introduce the concept of “profitability landscape”: a framework to analyze the trade-off between increasing

the share of self-consumption and increasing the system cost by implementing demand flexibility measures, such as batteries, smart appliances, or any other complementary investments that allows prosumers to increase their self-consumption share (Section 4). Finally, we perform a regression analysis to unveil the details of this trade-off to evaluate in what extent investments to increase demand flexibility are profitable.

2. Photovoltaic self-consumption regulation and profitability

2.1. Evolution of PVSC regulation

Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs) and subsidies were the main support policies to promote rooftop PV when its levelized cost (LCOE) was higher than retail prices (Dusonchet and Telaretti, 2015; Spertino et al., 2013). As PV costs decline and PV achieves “grid-parity” (the point at which LCOE equals retail prices, see Breyer and Gerlach (2013)), PV becomes profitable for self-consumption under certain circumstances (Chiaroni et al., 2014; Escobar et al., 2020; Lang et al., 2016). Whether PVSC is profitable depends, in addition to costs and insolation, on the specific PVSC regulation. Because the PV generation profile does not coincide with residential consumption patterns, some of the self-generated electricity is self-consumed, but the remaining electricity is exported to the grid. For this reason, whether PVSC is profitable depends on the structure of the retail tariff (that determines the potential savings of self-consumption) on the one hand, and on the price at which the surplus electricity is sold to the grid on the other hand.

At the beginning of the development of PVSC, many jurisdictions implemented net metering policies, in which the surplus electricity is valued at the same price as the retail electricity bought from the grid (see, e.g. the case of the California net metering system (Darghouth et al., 2011; Ros and Sai, 2023)). On the other hand, many jurisdictions did not allow selling the surplus electricity to grid, which made PVSC economically unfeasible due to the mismatch between demand and supply. Finally, selling the electricity to the grid at some price between zero and the retail price is becoming the most common policy, either by direct sale or by net billing when the benefits from selling the electricity are directly discounted from the bill. De Boeck et al. (2016) provides a review of the existing PVSC, López Prol and Steininger (2017) analyze the effect of these three types of policies on prosumers’ profitability, and the IEA Photovoltaic Power Systems Programme provides a review and methodology for the analysis of PVSC regulations (Masson et al., 2016a, 2016b).

2.2. Competitive PVSC

PVSC regulation involves multiple elements, such as access to distribution grids, conditions for shared self-consumption across multiple final consumers, etc. (Masson et al., 2016a, 2016b). One of the main policy choices is whether prosumers can sell their surplus electricity to the grid and at what price. The price at which the surplus electricity is sold to the grid is an important parameter because the consumption profile of prosumers differs from the PV generation pattern. For this reason, prosumers will usually be connected to the electricity grid, consume electricity from the grid when demand is higher than PV generation, and sell to the grid otherwise. PVSC is profitable when the savings derived from self-consumption and the revenues of selling the excess electricity to the grid are higher than the cost of the system. The savings derived from self-consumption depend on the variable part of the retail price, which is the price that prosumers would have to pay if they had to buy the electricity from the grid.

When PV cost was high, governments provided Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs) higher than the variable part of the retail price. In this case, prosumers do not have any incentive to self-consume, as the value of selling electricity to the grid is higher than the value they would obtain from self-consumption. When the levelized cost of PVSC systems declines below the variable part of the retail price, PVSC becomes profitable under a net metering regulation, in which the surplus electricity exported to the grid is remunerated at the (variable part of the) retail price. Net metering is an implicit subsidy to prosumers because the electricity exported to the grid is valued at the variable part of the retail price, which usually includes other costs in addition to the cost of energy itself. Additionally, because in many countries fixed costs of the electricity system (such as transmission and distribution) are charged, at least partially, in the variable part of the retail price rather than the fixed one, net metering policies cause cross-subsidization (i.e. consumers pay part of the network cost caused by prosumers) from consumers to prosumers (Ansarin et al., 2020).

On the contrary, other countries do not allow the sale of surplus electricity to the electricity grid or do not remunerate prosumers for it. In this case, PVSC is usually not profitable unless prosumers can self-consume most of the electricity generated. If the surplus electricity is exported to the grid without remuneration, this “pure self-consumption” regulation entails an implicit tax to prosumers, as that exported electricity is then sold to other consumers.

Any other price would be possible between zero (pure self-consumption) and the variable part of the retail price (net metering). This type of self-consumption regulation is a net billing system, when the value of the exported electricity is discounted from the electricity bill, or a direct sale

system when the surplus electricity is directly sold either to the wholesale market, to the retailer at an agreed price, or to any other entity through power purchase agreements (PPA) or contracts for differences (CFD). Figure 1 summarizes the impacts of each type of policy on PVSC profitability: the lower the remuneration of the surplus electricity, the lower the PVSC profitability. If the price of the electricity sold to the grid is higher than the variable part of the retail price, there would not be self-consumption, as it would be more profitable to sell all the electricity at the FiT than self-consuming it. Exporting the surplus electricity to the grid at wholesale price would be the competitive situation. A price above/below that level would entail an implicit subsidy/tax to prosumers.

Figure 1. PVSC profitability depending on the price of the surplus electricity exported to the grid.

An economically efficient retail tariff (i.e. one that maximizes social welfare), reflects the actual costs of the system to the consumer (hence called “cost-reflective”), ensuring cost recovery by utilities and cost-minimizing incentives for consumers. The theoretical first-best tariff would consist of a fixed charge that covers fixed network costs, and a variable part equivalent to the marginal cost of providing each additional unit of electricity in each time and place, including any external costs (Borenstein and Davis, 2012; Naughton, 1986; Puller and West, 2013). Current retail tariffs are usually flat (i.e. price does not change hourly), part of the fixed costs of the grid are recovered through the variable part of the retail price, and externalities are only partially internalized. The main reasons for this tariff structure were the inability to measure hourly consumption with traditional meters, the protection of consumers against price volatility, and the incentive for energy conservation. External costs are also difficult to estimate and implement. We now have the ability to measure hourly consumption with smart meters and estimate

external costs, demand flexibility becomes more important to integrate increasing shares of variable renewables, and high marginal (relative to fixed) prices discourage electrification (Schittekatte et al., 2022). For these reasons, fixing these inefficiencies becomes more relevant to speed up the energy transition at minimum possible cost.

The European Commission outlined the principles to integrate PVSC in competitive retail markets (European Commission, 2015). For PVSC to compete in equal conditions with any other technology, the retail electricity tariff has to reflect actual costs of providing electricity, and the surplus electricity has to be remunerated at the wholesale price. We thus analyze a competitive PVSC market situation according to these principles: cost-reflectivity of retail tariffs and net billing self-consumption policy at the wholesale price including the currently internalized external costs (carbon prices affecting the wholesale market and environmental taxes on the retail price).

In a liberalized retail market, prosumers would be able to agree prices with the retailer or sell the surplus electricity to other consumers through power purchase agreements (PPA) or contracts for differences (CfD). Retail markets are highly regulated due to market failures related to asymmetric information, market power and consumer inattention. In this context, the government could set a default regulation in which the surplus electricity is remunerated at wholesale price, but prosumers could make any other arrangements with utilities or other consumers depending on their specific circumstances. A competitive PVSC regulation would thus require two elements: (i) that the variable price of the retail price comprises only the cost of providing energy (i.e. fixed costs should be charged in the fixed part of the retail price) and any associated external cost (e.g. toxic waste, carbon emissions or pollution)); and (ii) that the price of the exported electricity is set, by default, at the wholesale electricity price, unless prosumers make any other arrangement with a third party willing to buy that electricity at a different price.

In the next sections we evaluate the profitability of PVSC in Europe under a competitive framework that meets the two elements outlined above. First we present the data and methods (Section 3), then calculate PVSC internal rates of return (IRR) for each country in average conditions (Section 4, and ranges in the Appendix) and build profitability landscapes to assess the potential gains of demand flexibility (Section 5). Finally, we study in detail the trade-off between increasing the share of self-consumption and the cost of the system to analyze whether it pays off to invest in demand flexibility alongside the PVSC system (Section 6).

3. Data and methods

3.1. Data

According to the principles for competitive PVSC outlined above, we build our dataset as follows. We assume that the price of the surplus electricity exported to the grid is the average wholesale price. Because the PV generation pattern is correlated with demand, the value of PV electricity is higher than the average wholesale price at low penetration. As penetration increases, however, prices decline due to the merit-order effect (López Prol and Schill, 2021; Maciejowska, 2020; Martin de Lagarde and Lantz, 2018), and PV value declines even further due to the cannibalization effect (Hirth, 2015; Liebensteiner and Naumann, 2022; López Prol et al., 2020). The merit-order effect, however, is a short-term phenomenon, as prices will increase again as variable renewables displace baseload capacity (Léautier, 2019). Additionally, the cannibalization effect is expected to be mitigated by increasing system flexibility and the progressive internalization of external costs (Brown and Reichenberg, 2020). For this reason, we assume the average wholesale price with an annual 2% escalation rate in line with the European Central Bank long-term inflation objective.

The value of the self-consumed electricity is assumed to be the cost of the energy and supply component of the retail price, plus any renewable and environmental taxes, and including the country-specific VAT on this value for the residential segment. This is equivalent to assuming that the variable part of the retail price comprises only variable cost (including the externalities currently internalized), and any fixed cost of the system would be charged in the fixed part of the prosumer's electricity bill, so it would not be avoided by self-consumption (according to our cost-reflectivity assumption). We analyze two segments: residential (consumption band DC from 2,500 kWh to 4,999 kWh) and industrial (consumption band ID from 2,000 MWh to 19,999 MWh), according to Eurostat definitions.

We use data for the year 2019 or latest available before that year for both wholesale and retail prices to avoid the distortionary short-term effects of the pandemic in 2020-2021 and the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022. Figure 1 shows wholesale and residential and industrial retail prices according to the definitions above and Table A.1 in the Appendix presents all country-specific data and respective data sources.

Figure 2. Electricity prices in Europe in 2019 or latest available before that year. Wholesale prices (European Commission). Retail prices for the residential (consumption band DC from 2,500 kWh to 4,999 kWh) and industrial (consumption band ID from 2,000 MWh to 19,999 MWh) segments (Eurostat), including “energy and supply”, “renewable taxes” and “environmental taxes” components and applying country-specific VAT to the sum of the three components for the residential segment.

The results presented in Section 4 do not reflect actual PVSC profitability levels, but the average profitability in a hypothetical competitive PVSC scenario, with equal system costs and self-consumption shares across countries. We also provide profitability landscapes in Section 5 and in the Appendix that allow readers to estimate PVSC profitability for the whole range of plausible PVSC system costs and self-consumption shares. For the baseline results, we assume PVSC system cost of 1 and 1.5 €/Wp (low range of the IEA-PVPS trends report 2022); and a self-consumption share of 50% and 35%, for the industrial and residential segments, respectively. We assume that the investment is self-financed to exclude the effect of different financing conditions across countries, and a 25-year system lifetime with an annual degradation rate of 0.8%. Annual operation and maintenance cost are assumed to be 1% of the system cost with the same 2% annual escalation rate.

3.2. Methods

We assess PVSC profitability with the internal rate of return (IRR): the discount rate at which the net present value of the investment over its lifetime equals zero. This indicator is the most suitable for this type of analysis, because it is relative, and thus comparable, irrespective of the investment amount or maturity, with any other type of investment, and it does not require us to make arbitrary assumptions about the discount rate. This is particularly relevant as different agents have different discount rates (e.g. households have different profitability requirements than companies or energy communities), and interest rates also change across countries and over time.

The method to calculate PVSC is described in detail in López Prol and Steininger (2020, 2017) so we do not reproduce it here, but the code and data to replicate these results are publicly available (see data availability section). In addition to the IRR values in Section 4, we also provide “profitability landscapes” in Section 5 by calculating “IRR thresholds” and illustrating them in contour plots. Finally, we perform a series of regressions that will be explained in detail in the corresponding sections.

4. Competitive PVSC

This section presents the profitability of competitive PVSC in Europe according to the principles outlined in Section 2.2 and the assumptions and data showed in Section 3.1 and Table A.1 in the Appendix. In this framework, prosumers sell the surplus electricity (50% and 65% for industrial and residential segments, respectively) at wholesale price, and the value of the electricity self-consumed is the cost of energy and supply plus renewable energy and environmental taxes (plus the corresponding VAT for the residential segment). The system cost is assumed to be 1 €/Wp for the industrial segment and 1.5 €/Wp for the residential segment.

Figure 3 shows the PVSC profitability results for both segments across countries in average conditions. Figure A.1 in the Appendix provides the corresponding ranges depicting the insolation (amount of solar resource) variation within each country. The maps in Figure 3 give an overview of the maturity of PVSC under a competitive regulatory framework and its drivers. The main determinant of PVSC profitability is insolation, which translates into higher profitability the lower the latitude. The industrial segment has consistently higher profitability levels than the residential segment due to lower system costs and higher self-consumption share, despite lower retail prices (see Figure 2). At the assumed costs and prices, industrial PVSC is competitive in all Europe except the Nordic countries. Residential PVSC is not competitive in the Nordic countries due to low insolation, but also in the Baltic and Eastern European countries, due to

the low internalization of fossil fuel external costs. As external costs continue to be progressively internalized and PV costs continue to decline, PVSC profitability is expected to increase in the future.

Figure 3. Competitive PVSC average profitability (internal rate of return) across countries. See Figure A.1 in the Appendix for a profitability range depending on insolation.

5. Profitability landscapes

Solar insolation and both wholesale and retail prices are exogenous to prosumers, meaning that they cannot influence them. Prosumers can, however, decide on their PVSC system configuration to optimize the trade-off between system cost and the share of self-consumption. For instance, if there is a large difference between wholesale and retail price, prosumers have higher incentives to undersize their system to increase profitability by maximizing their self-consumption share, at the cost of potentially lower total profits. On the opposite, under a net metering scheme (the value of the exported electricity is the variable part of the retail price), prosumers would have incentives to oversize their system as much as possible to maximize both profitability (due to lower unit cost) and total profits (due to higher production). Profitability landscapes are useful illustrate potential PVSC profitability depending on the two variables prosumers can influence with their decisions: system cost and self-consumption share.

System costs comprise the cost of modules, balance of systems and installation. Additionally, the present cost of any device that helps increase self-consumption, such as batteries or smart devices, can be included in this framework to assess whether the increase in self-consumption compensates for the higher system cost. To illustrate the concept and interpretation of the profitability landscape, Figure 4 shows the case of Spain for the industrial and residential

segments. Profitability landscapes are contour plots in which the lines represent profitability thresholds depending on system cost and the self-consumption share. The lower system cost and the higher self-consumption share toward the bottom right of the figure, the higher the profitability and vice versa.

Figure 4. Profitability landscapes: internal rate of return (lines from 0% (light solid on the top) to 20% (dark dashed at the bottom)) depending on the share of self-consumption and the installation cost. See country and sector specific profitability landscapes in Figure A.2. in the Appendix.

As also shown in Figure 3, Figure 4 shows that industrial segment has higher profitability than the residential segment due to its higher self-consumption share. At the same self-consumption share, however, the residential segment would have higher profitability due to the higher retail prices. The slope of the profitability thresholds is higher for the residential than for the industrial segment because the difference between the retail and the wholesale prices is also higher (see Figure 2). For this reason, increasing the share of self-consumption provides higher benefits for the residential segment than for the industrial segment, everything else equal.

The profitability thresholds are not parallel, which indicates the nonlinear relation between profitability and system cost for any given self-consumption share. As system cost declines, profitability increases more than proportionally. Likewise, the profitability thresholds are closer to each other at lower self-consumption shares, and they diverge as the self-consumption share increases, which entails that the impact of system cost declines is stronger at low self-consumption shares.

The points in Figure 4 represent the average baseline situation depicted in Figure 3. Residential IRR in this case is ~5% (5.2% precisely). The landscape shows that profitability would be the same (5%) if the self-consumption share increases to ~62.5% and system cost to ~2€/Wp, i.e. we can profitably double our system cost (e.g. by installing batteries) if that allows us to self-consume more than 62.5% of our generation. The slope of the IRR lines, therefore, indicates the relationship between the share of self-consumption and the system cost.

6. The value of demand flexibility

Figure 4 shows that the slope of the IRR thresholds in the profitability landscape provides a cost-benefit appraisal of whether demand flexibility is profitable by comparing the additional system cost to the benefits derived from a higher self-consumption share. In this section, we study this trade-off in detail by first estimating the slopes of the IRR thresholds for each profitability level to then explain their determinants.

The slope of the IRR in the profitability landscape tells us by how much we can increase our system cost per percentage point increase in the share of self-consumption maintaining the same level of profitability. That is, it indicates the marginal returns of demand flexibility (measured as 1 p.p. increase in the self-consumption share) in terms of €/Wp of potential additional investment. If the increase in the system cost is lower than the IRR slope, then the additional investment is profitable because the benefits derived from higher self-consumption are higher than the increase in the system cost.

We thus estimate the slope β of multiple IRR thresholds within the range between -10% and 30% in the profitability landscape for each country and segment, which is the increase in system cost (€/Wp) per percentage point increase in the self-consumption share. Figure 5 illustrates the slopes for each country and segment for each level of profitability (IRR), highlighting the average across countries for each segment. This figure provides two insights: (i) diminishing marginal returns of flexibility (the IRR slope declines as IRR increases, as it can also be observed in the profitability landscapes), and (ii) the higher potential gains of flexibility for the residential segment (due to the higher difference between wholesale and retail prices, see Figure 2). The figure implies that increasing the share of self-consumption is very valuable to achieve positive returns, but as profitability increases the marginal returns of flexibility decline.

Figure 5. Marginal returns of demand flexibility for each country (light lines) and average (dark lines) for each level of profitability (IRR, %).

To further explain the drivers of these observed dynamics, we run two additional regressions for each segment:

$$\hat{\beta}_i = \alpha + \gamma_1 IRR_i + \gamma_2 PV_i + \gamma_3 Wholesale_i + \gamma_4 Retail_i + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{\beta}_i = \alpha + \zeta_1 IRR_i + \zeta_2 PV_i + \zeta_3 Gap_i + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Where the dependent variable $\hat{\beta}_i$ is the slope of the IRR threshold estimated from the profitability landscapes for each country i and shown in Figure 5, IRR_i is the value of the internal rate of return for each threshold in percentage, PV_i is the average annual PV yield in each country in Wh/kWp, $Wholesale_i$ and $Retail_i$ are the respective prices for each country, and Gap_i is the difference between retail and wholesale prices, in €/kWh.

Table 1 shows the results of these regressions. Given that the dependent variable is the slope of the IRR in the profitability landscape, the regression coefficients can be read as unit impact of each independent variable on the value of demand flexibility (understood as the potential increase in system cost per percentage point increase in self-consumption share). Thus, one percentage point increase in the IRR decreases value of demand flexibility by 99 €/kWp for the residential segment and 54 €/kWp for the industrial segment. This confirms the diminishing

marginal returns on demand flexibility: the higher the profitability, the lower the additional potential returns of increasing the self-consumption share. The diminishing marginal returns are stronger for the residential than for the industrial segments, but that may be simply because the potential gains of demand flexibility are also higher for the residential segment (Figure 5).

Countries with higher insolation have higher potential returns on demand flexibility. For each additional Wh/kWp of annual PV production, the value of flexibility increases by between 1.4 and 1.6 €/Wp. This is because we define the value of demand flexibility as the potential increase of system cost per percentage point increase in the self-consumption share. Thus, the higher the PV yield, the higher the impact of increasing the share of electricity self-consumed given installed capacity. Because countries with higher insolation will generally have also higher PVSC profitability, these two effects counter each other.

The main market factor affecting the value of demand flexibility is the difference between retail and wholesale electricity prices. When this spread increases by 1 €/kWh, the value of flexibility increases by 49 €/kWp in the industrial and 229 €/kWp in the residential segments (columns 3 and 4 in Table 1, respectively). This can also be observed by looking at wholesale and retail prices separately (columns 1 and 2 in Table 1). Higher wholesale prices reduce the value and thus the incentive for self-consumption, while higher retail prices increase it. Because retail prices are generally higher for residential than for industrial consumers, all price effects are also stronger for the residential segment.

IRR slope (Δ in system cost (€/Wp) per pp Δ in self-consumption)				
	Industrial (1)	Residential (2)	Industrial (3)	Residential (4)
IRR (%)	-0.054*** (0.001)	-0.099*** (0.003)	-0.054*** (0.001)	-0.099*** (0.002)
PV yield (Wh/kWp)	1.510*** (0.118)	1.462*** (0.209)	1.413*** (0.102)	1.642*** (0.160)
Wholesale price (€/kWh)	-0.164*** (0.035)	-0.204*** (0.062)		
Retail price (€/kWh)	0.064*** (0.006)	0.178*** (0.011)		
Retail-wholesale spread (€/kWh)			0.049*** (0.006)	0.229*** (0.009)
Constant	-0.107 (0.156)	0.100 (0.276)	-0.485*** (0.119)	-0.870*** (0.185)
Observations	1,350	1,350	1,350	1,350
R ²	0.552	0.567	0.540	0.655
Adjusted R ²	0.551	0.566	0.539	0.654
Residual Std. Error	0.839 (df = 1345)	1.488 (df = 1345)	0.851 (df = 1346)	1.327 (df = 1346)
F Statistic	415.096*** (df = 4; 1345)	440.320*** (df = 4; 1345)	526.369*** (df = 3; 1346)	852.825*** (df = 3; 1346)
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01			

Table 1. Regression results for each segment for equations 1 (columns 1-2) and 2 (columns 3-4).

7. Conclusions and policy implications

Photovoltaic self-consumption (PVSC) is a central part of the energy transition but retail electricity tariffs have not adapted to enhance its competitive integration in the electricity system. As PVSC costs decline, subsidies tend to be phased out in favor of more sustainable regulatory schemes that allow fair competition in equal conditions among generating technologies. A cost-reflective retail tariff and a competitive PVSC regulation would entail selling the surplus electricity at wholesale price, and paying for the grid electricity only the marginal cost of energy and supply, including external costs (i.e. prosumers should not avoid paying the fixed cost of the grid by self-consumption).

We first assess how much would be the profitability of PVSC in Europe in a competitive regulatory environment (Figures 3 and A.1). PVSC provides positive returns in average conditions in most countries except the Nordic countries due to low insolation and Baltic and Eastern countries due to the low internalization of externalities. As external costs of fossil fuels are progressively internalized, PVSC profitability will increase.

We then introduce the concept of profitability landscape, that allows prosumers to evaluate potential returns depending on the share of self-consumption and the system cost. Because these are the two main endogenous variables for prosumers, this type of evaluation may help deciding whether additional investment in demand flexibility (e.g. batteries or smart appliances) are profitable given prices and insolation.

Finally, we study in detail the value of demand flexibility for prosumers by looking at the trade-off between the benefits derived from increasing the self-consumption share versus the additional system cost of coupling the PVSC system with other demand flexibility investments. We confirm the diminishing marginal returns of flexibility and quantify the effect of the main variables (profitability, PV yield and wholesale and retail prices) on the value of flexibility.

Our results confirm the competitiveness of PVSC in Europe when external cost are (partially) internalized and provide additional tools to evaluate the profitability of PVSC and the value of demand flexibility. Further research could integrate actual external costs in this framework and extend the analysis to other markets.

Data availability

Replication package, including data and code (in R) available on Zenodo:
[10.5281/zenodo.8154910](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154910).

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Declaration of competing interests

None.

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Appendix

Country	VAT (%)	Industrial (€/kWh)	Residential (€/kWh)	Wholesale (€/kWh)	PV yield (Wh/Wp y ⁻¹)
Austria	20	4.968	8.297	4.110	994
Belgium	21	5.322	9.336	4.796	928
Bulgaria	20	5.610	6.253	3.728	1223
Croatia	25	4.770	7.361	5.192	1178
Czechia	21	4.566	7.059	4.092	942
Denmark	25	4.056	6.211	3.915	908
Estonia	20	3.943	5.308	4.140	864
Finland	24	4.456	6.896	4.234	790
France	20	4.423	7.487	4.494	1135
Germany	19	4.682	8.951	4.025	938
Greece	24	6.772	10.575	5.538	1423
Hungary	27	5.568	6.703	4.848	1117
Ireland	23	7.988	15.144	5.880	880
Italy	22	7.843	12.090	6.148	1313
Latvia	21	4.870	5.556	4.471	881
Lithuania	21	4.810	5.510	4.525	1172
Malta	18	11.611	13.418	7.826	1617
Netherlands	21	5.145	8.768	4.687	931
Norway	25	3.718	6.130	3.750	813
Poland	23	4.861	6.588	4.453	939
Portugal	23	5.625	8.048	4.880	1497
Romania	19	4.306	4.940	4.382	1122
Slovakia	20	4.793	6.666	4.207	1000
Slovenia	22	5.245	7.055	4.865	1083
Spain	21	7.508	13.637	4.861	1461
Sweden	25	4.275	6.598	3.901	813
UK	20	7.255	13.933	5.453	865
Sources	Multiple	Eurostat (nrg_pc_204_c & nrg_pc_205_c)	European Commission	PVGIS	

Table A.1. Country-specific data.

Figure A.1. Profitability ranges depending on insolation range for each country (see table A.1).

Figure A.2. Industrial profitability landscapes across countries (see Figure 4).

Figure A.3. Residential profitability landscapes across countries (see Figure 4).

Figure A.4. Marginal returns of demand flexibility (see Figure 5).